

Yield potential

Effect on grain yield of shoot removal at different stages of rice crop growth

P. S. S. Murthy, P. J. R. Reddy, and S. S. R. Prasad, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Maruteru 534122, West Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh (AP), India

Damage to rice tillers by severe incidence of pests, diseases, rodents, etc. can occur at any stage of crop growth. Tiller number determines panicle number, and tiller damage can lead to reduced yield.

We laid out a 1989 wet season field trial in a split-plot design with two replications, with two varieties in the main plots, three crop stages in the subplots, and seven shoot removal treatments in the sub-subplots.

Single seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Shoots were removed by cutting aerial shoots 2 cm above the soil surface. Standard cultural

Effect of shoot removal on grain yield.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (g/m ²)							
	Swarna				Chaitanya			
	AT	PI	Fl	Mean	AT	PI	Fl	Mean
No shoots	408	122	0	177	394	59	0	151
Main shoot alone	459	193	68	240	396	116	91	201
Main shoot + 1 tiller	556	342	173	357	564	259	173	332
Main shoot + 3 tillers	664	463	363	497	601	418	316	445
Main shoot + 5 tillers	698	578	480	585	605	503	403	504
Main shoot + 7 tillers	699	733	494	642	614	608	535	586
Control (has main shoot + all tillers)	781	825	692	766	618	725	713	685
Mean	609	465	324		542	383	319	
Mean for stages	: AT	= 576;	PI	= 424;	Fl	= 322		
LSD (0.05)	: V	= ns;	V in S.P	= 33;	SSP in SP	= 68		
	SP	= 18;	SP in V	= 25;	SSP in V	= ns		
	SSP	= 39;	SP in SSP	= 97;	V in SSP	= ns		
	V = varieties,		SP = stages.		SSP = treatments			

^a Shoots were removed at active tillering (AT), panicle initiation (PI), and flowering (F1).

practices and plant protection measures were applied.

Grain yield was reduced by shoot removal (see table). This indicates that tiller losses at any stage of crop growth will lead to a yield reduction.

Shoot removal at flowering was most detrimental (25-100% reduction in yield),

followed by shoot removal at panicle initiation (11.2-91.9%) and at active tillering (0.6-47.8%). At active tillering of Chaitanya, maintaining at least four tillers (including the main shoot) did not affect yield. This could indicate that not all the tillers produced were needed. ■

Submergence tolerance and kneeing ability of some rainfed lowland rices

N. K. Sarma (present address: Horticultural Research Station, Assam Agricultural University [AAU], Kahikuchi, P.O. Azara, Guwahati-17, Assam) and M. H. Hazarika, Plant Breeding and Genetics Department, AAU, Jorhat 13, Assam, India

In many monsoon areas, rainfed ricefields may be submerged 1-7 d or longer at a time. Submergence tolerance is needed for crop survival.

We conducted two separate trials during 1986, to evaluate submergence tolerance and kneeing ability of eight local deepwater lines, four derivatives of crosses between high-yielding varieties and a local deepwater rice, and one improved winter rice (Manoharsali). The experiments were laid out in randomized block designs with three replications.

To test submergence tolerance, 10-d-old seedlings were submerged in

Submergence tolerance and kneeing ability of rice genotypes. Assam, India, 1986.

Cultivar	Pedigree	Submergence tolerance (%)	Kneeing ability (°angle)
AR9	Local deepwater line	58.5	37.1
Padmapani	Local deepwater line	88.5	43.9
Herepi Bao	Local deepwater line	75.0	26.5
Rona Bao	Local deepwater line	66.5	35.8
Ranga Bao	Local deepwater line	88.5	30.0
Itakhulig	Local deepwater line	36.5	27.6
Dubraj	Local deepwater line	51.5	32.3
Sarsuri Bao	Local deepwater line	65.0	37.6
PJNB95-2	Pankaj/Jagannath/Negheri Bao	60.0	28.9
PJNB96-10	Pankaj/Jagannath/Negheri Bao	65.0	39.6
PN42	Pankajmegheri Bao	61.5	37.4
PN54	Pankajmegheri Bao	66.5	33.2
Manoharsali	Winter rice	41.5	15.9
LSD (0.05)		2.3	2.0
CV (%)		10.9	3.5

30-cm water for 10 d and survival recorded 7 d after the water receded. For kneeing ability, plants were uprooted 10 d after sowing (but before flowering) and laid horizontally on a puddled bed with 2-cm-deep water. Kneeing was measured 8 d later.

Padmapani and Ranga Bao had the highest submergence tolerance (88.5%)

(see table). All cultivars except Manoharsali and Itakhulig had >50% survival.

Padmapani had the highest kneeing angle (43.90°); Manoharsali, a winter rice, the lowest (15.900).

Six genotypes had both superior submergence tolerance (>58.5%) and kneeing ability (>35°). ■